

Catalogue of Soundscape Interventions

Technical report for soundscape design taxonomy
January 2024

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Part 1

Introduction of the Catalogue of Soundscape Intervention(CSI)

Introduction

Since the late 1960s soundscape studies have been rising steadily as a research field with an increased growth rate in the last 20 years approximately. Indeed, looking at the scientific production published in peer-reviewed international journals for the last two decades, one can observe a significant increase in the number of items published on soundscape with a focus on urban scenarios (i.e., excluding naturalistic and marine soundscapes and other very specific applications where the term soundscape is used).

The rationale for this project is to provide a tool for data collection and communication and to streamline the process of selecting examples of projects/interventions/sites of cultural valence in public spaces around the world that are meaningful in terms of “soundscape approach” and are directly or indirectly driven by it. The ultimate goal is to observe frequent/recurring situations or strategies that can be collated into a “design toolkit” and formulate “design briefs” that local authorities will be using to communicate with soundscape consultants/researchers. A “design toolkit”, developed based on data reflecting successful measures implemented in many countries around the world, may also become an informative source for the standardization process currently taking place within the ISO 12913 series.

Aims and Objectives

The general aim of the Catalogue of Soundscape Interventions project is to develop a data collection tool and to create a knowledge base of sites and places around the world where specific measures have been put in place to a) design and/or curate the acoustic environment and its corresponding soundscape or b) to inform the future development of soundscape design and practice. These will be achieved by pursuing the following objectives:

WP1 - Website and Data Collection Tool:

- ❖ Developing a tool for data collection
- ❖ Creating an online catalogue of soundscape design examples

WP2 - Soundscape Design Taxonomy:

- ❖ Identifying recurring intervention patterns and levels
- ❖ Defining a taxonomy of soundscape strategies
- ❖ Releasing a technical report

WP3 - Outreach and Impact:

- ❖ Raising awareness on the benefits of soundscape design
- ❖ Bridging academia and industry
- ❖ Dissemination of research findings in conferences and journals

Work packages

The project is meant to run for 2 years, with some parts of it extending beyond its life cycle, depending on the capacity of the project team members to attract further funding and making it self-sustaining in the medium- to long-term. This is based on the understanding that most efforts are related to the set-up of the project and will be condensed in the first 12-18 months of activity.

Work Packages (WP) with connecting tasks/processes put in context for the life time of the CSI project; WP1 potentially extends beyond the 2-year horizon

WP1: Website and data collection tool

The CSI Project website, led by TUB, is complete. It features a Wordpress-based system with Google Maps API, SSL certificates, and a user-friendly layout. The site includes a mission statement, soundscape design examples, contact information, a submission form, and a geo-referenced map. Optimized for mobile use, it allows global contributions of text, visuals, and audio. The site has an automated review process, regular maintenance, and backup systems, ensuring quality and consistency in showcasing cultural valence in public spaces influenced by the soundscape approach.

WP2: Soundscape Design Taxonomy

Once enough soundscape design examples are uploaded to the website, a preliminary review will occur to inform WP2, aiming to identify common design approaches and challenges. This will form a Soundscape Design Taxonomy with multiple classification layers, like conservation actions and user impact. Consultations with stakeholders—community groups, NGOs, designers, researchers, and government agencies—will ensure diverse perspectives and consensus. The taxonomy will serve as a design toolkit for local authorities to guide soundscape consultants. Led by UCL, the project will periodically update the taxonomy, publish preliminary results for visibility, and integrate the final taxonomy into the project website as a technical report.

WP3: Outreach and impact

This project's Work Package (WP) spans its entire duration, encompassing the promotion of an online catalogue (mainly under WP1) and integration with WP3 for broader dissemination. WP3 focuses on crafting a social media strategy, selecting and managing appropriate channels. Early efforts will leverage the International Year of Sound initiative for wider public reach. Activities include participation in conferences and webinars, community engagement through soundscapes contests and polls, and embedding project outcomes in UCL and TUB curricula, offering thesis research opportunities. Collaboration with the ISO/TC 43/SC 1/WG 54 ensures alignment with ISO 12913 standards. UCL and TUB jointly lead this WP.

Looking forward

As we look forward, the vision for this project encompasses both its expansion and longevity beyond the initial two-year timeframe. A key aim is to sustain the project website for at least five years, establishing it as a dynamic hub for ongoing submissions and a valuable resource for online teaching and educational activities. By integrating the curation of content into Master thesis and dissertation projects, the effort required to maintain this online presence is expected to be minimal, fostering a self-sustaining and continuously enriching educational platform.

Looking ahead, the project is set to evolve into CSI+, a follow-up initiative focusing on documenting select case studies through audio-visual recordings in line with ISO/TS 12913-2:2018 standards. This initiative will build upon the knowledge and experience gained from earlier projects, such as the ERC Advanced Grant “Soundscape Indices” and “Urban Soundscapes of the World.” The goal is to select sites that offer a balance of reachability, originality, and cost-effective documentation, further enriching the CSI website with high-quality audio-visual materials and reinforcing its status as a premier educational and research resource in soundscape design.

Introducing the eight dimensions of soundscape intervention

The analysis of the existing 43 real-world soundscape interventions (retrieved in Jan 2024) in the database revealed eight distinct but interrelated dimensions that comprehensively characterize these interventions, including their:

- **STAGE**
- **CONTRIBUTORS**
- **SCALE**
- **PERIOD OF TIME**
- **INTERVENTION TYPES**
- **PUBLIC INVOLVEMENT**
- **AIMS AND PURPOSE**
- **APPROACHES**

Each dimension, while distinct, intersects and influences the others, contributing to a holistic understanding of the soundscape interventions. When new projects are added to the database, the taxonomy will be updated to ensure its accuracy and completeness. We hope that this taxonomy will help stakeholders such as local governments, soundscape consultants, and researchers in communicating and cooperating to improve the sound environment.

The eight dimensions of soundscape interventions

How to use this Catalogue

The Catalogue of Soundscape Interventions (CSI) is a multifaceted platform that serves as both a repository and a tool for a wide array of users interested in the acoustic qualities of environments. Here's an overarching view of what the CSI enables users to do:

- 1. Case Retrieval:** Users can search and retrieve detailed examples of soundscape interventions from around the world. This includes data on various soundscapes that have been designed or curated to enhance the acoustic environment.
- 2. Comparative Analysis:** The platform allows for the comparison of different cases, enabling users to understand the varied approaches taken in different contexts and the outcomes of these interventions.
- 3. New Case Submission:** CSI encourages the submission of new cases. Users can document and share their own soundscape interventions, contributing to the richness and diversity of the database.

The general aim of the CSI is twofold: to assemble a data collection tool that can capture a comprehensive knowledge base of acoustic interventions globally, and to foster the growth of soundscapes as a field of study and practice. It aims to catalog sites and places where measures have been implemented to either shape or inform the auditory environment, serving as a reference for future design and practice in the field.

Here's how different people can engage with the CSI:

- **Academic researchers** can use the platform for gathering data, conducting analyses, and contributing scholarly work.
- **Urban planners and designers** can reference case studies for inspiration and document the evolution and impact of their projects.
- **Sound artists and designers** are provided with a wealth of soundscapes for creative exploration and are encouraged to share their auditory projects.
- **Environmental activists** can find and promote examples of noise mitigation and sound ecology, and connect with others to advocate for acoustic environmentalism.
- **Educators and students** can utilize the CSI as a teaching tool and repository for student projects, bridging the gap between theory and application.
- **Local government and policymakers** can inform their decisions with data from the catalogue.
- **Community groups and NGOs** can use the catalogue to drive community-centric projects and find collaborators for soundscape enhancement.
- **Industry professionals** can keep abreast of best practices, showcase their work, and find business opportunities through the platform.
- **The general public** can learn about soundscapes, contribute to the community discourse, and share their own experiences with sound in their environments.

Part 2

The CSI online platform

SHEAF SQUARE IN SHEFFIELD, UNITED KINGDOM

This installation at Sheaf Square in Sheffield, United Kingdom was implemented in 2006. Promoted by residents and local authorities, it is a permanent installation. Designed by SI Applied Ltd.

In the audio example you can hear the sounds created by the water installations at Sheaf Square.

Cutting Edge in Sheffield

2006

CONTEXT

This square, positioned between the A61 major trunk road and the Sheffield train station, features a dynamic system of water fountains and the Cutting Edge Sculpture, acting as a noise barrier while masking water sounds. It serves as the main entrance to the station and the city. The installation was built as part of the general reshaping of the area [1].

References

[1] Oberman, T., Jambrošić, K., Horvat, M., & Bojanić Obad Šćitaroci, B. (2020). *Using Virtual Soundwalk Approach for Assessing Sound Art Soundscape Interventions in Public Spaces*. *Applied Sciences*, 10(6), 2102. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10062102>

Screenshot of the website (<https://soundscape-intervention.org/ex-sheaf-square/>)
Showing an example of soundscape intervention practice.

General platform architecture

The Catalogue of Soundscape Interventions, launched in early 2022 at soundscapeintervention.org, serves as an online repository and data collection tool for soundscape projects. Aimed at researchers, professionals, local communities, and the general public, it facilitates public participation and networking. The website features a catalogue and submission form, with the catalogue providing a global overview of soundscape projects, pinpointed on a custom world map using Google My Maps API. Each project has a dedicated subpage with detailed information, including background, implementation date, observations, and supplementary materials like audio, pictures, and publications. The site also includes a search feature for easy navigation.

Catalogue - Case overview

An overview of the locations on the world map of the 43 sites presently included in the Catalogue of Soundscape Interventions, as of November 2023 (<https://soundscapeintervention.org/catalogue/>)

Submission form

Please provide the following information:

Soundscape name *

What is the name of the soundscape project/intervention/cultural heritage site? If a name is not applicable, please insert a location.

Soundscape location *

Please insert lat/long geodata, if available. Otherwise specify the location as precisely as possible, i.e. road, city, country.

Brief description of intervention *

What was the reason for the soundscape intervention? Please give a brief description of the context (background of intervention). What were challenges and ambitions? What were the outcomes, if available? [max. 200 words]

Detailed soundscape strategies

What soundscape strategies were used? Please give a more detailed description, if available, i.e. masking of unwanted noise/sound enrichment, preserving local identity and or soundmarks, increasing public awareness or other (please specify). [max. 400 words]

Status of implementation *

ongoing

Date of implementation *

Initiators and participants

residents businesses local authorities national authorities/agencies (e.g. heritage) others

Were soundscape designers/researchers involved in this process?

Yes

If yes, who was involved?

Name of involved person(s).

Typical audience

residents tourists commuters workers students other

Observations after implementation

What observations have been made after the implementation? i.e. improved assessments, more users, less anti-social behaviour, other...

Has this intervention been documented?

Yes

If yes, where can the documentation be found?

URL of documentation

Upload material (max. 3 files and 60 MB; allowed formats: jpg, png, gif, pdf, wav, mp3) *

No file chosen

I'm not a robot

First name / Last name *

E-mail *

Upload terms *

I hereby certify that the material I upload complies with the [Terms and Conditions](#) and that I do not infringe third-party rights.

Submit

Screen shot of the submission form, August 2023(<https://soundscape-intervention.org/submissions/>). A PDF version of the submission form is available on the website.

Submission Form Accessibility:

- Available to all website visitors, no registration needed.
- Each submission gets a unique ID.
- Data collected in an online database, exportable offline.

Data Collection Threshold:

- Set low to encourage early and frequent use.

Form Details:

- Contains 18 items.
- 14 items gather details about soundscapes (name, location, date, status, description, rationale, involved parties, target audience, methods, observations).
- Includes text fields, drop-downs, checkboxes (single/multiple choice).
- Mandatory items: name, location, basic description, implementation date/status.

Submission Requirements:

Must upload visual/audio material.

Confirm no third-party copyright infringement.

Purpose of Visual/Audio Information:

- Verify project's existence.
- Generate content for a catalogue.

Case review and selection criteria

Review process

In regular, predefined intervals, submitted entries are exported to an offline format following submission and undergo a manual review process, see Figure 3. After the export, the first step in this task chain is a quality screen to check whether entries match the required criteria for inclusion into the catalogue or not. Inadmissible entries are excluded from further review and are consequently removed from the database. If the entry is not blatantly inadmissible but fails to meet quality standards and legal requirements, the submitting party is contacted and asked to resubmit the entry with revised information. Entries that pass the screening are qualitatively analyzed and published on the website.

Schematic representation of the review process.

Criteria for describing a soundscape interventions

Review Process Overview:

- Two steps: initial screening and criteria identification.
- Both steps use a binary checklist for simplicity and objectivity.

Screening Checklist:

- Consists of 8 yes/no questions.
- First 4 items must be affirmative for entry acceptance.
- Negative responses lead to removal (e.g., duplicates, invalid information).

- If items 5-8 are negative, re-submission may be requested.

Criteria Identification Checklist:

- Used for qualitative analysis.
- Helps define "soundscape intervention" using real-world examples.
- Aims to develop a taxonomy based on quality indicators.
- Includes 7 yes/no items, with ongoing refinement.

Scoring System:

- No minimum score for inclusion in the catalogue.
- Cumulative scoring, higher score indicates higher quality.
- Used internally, not published on the website.

Topic	Item #	Checklist item
<i>Basic Information</i>		
Contact	1	Has the submitting party provided real contact information?
Content	2	Is the data free of any harmful/inappropriate/offensive content?
Soundscape name	3	Does the soundscape project/intervention have an identifiable name/title?
Soundscape location	4	Has an exact location of the project/intervention been provided?
Indicators	5	Is it clear who has initiated the project/intervention?
Date	6	Is it clear when the project/intervention was initiated/carried out?
<i>Metadata</i>		
Audio/picture	7	Does the provided audio/picture data have adequate quality?
Copyright	8	Is author- and ownership of the provided audio/picture data clear?

Screening checklist; each item receives a 0 1 score depending on whether the criterion is met or not.

Criteria	Item #	Checklist item
Methodology (Quality Indicators)		
Background	1	Has the reasoning/background for the project/intervention been sufficiently explained?
Aims & Objectives	2	Are the aims and objectives of the project/intervention clear?
Methods	3	Have typical soundscape strategies been used to carry out the project/intervention?
Data collection	4	Has data been collected with standardized methods?
Public involvement	5	Has the public been involved? i.e. advisory/cooperative/user-led involvement
Outcome	6	Has the outcome of the project/intervention been documented?
Peer review	7	Has the project/intervention been reported in peer-reviewed journals?

Criteria identification checklist; each item receives a 0-1 score depending on whether the criterion are met or not.

Existing database

The existing database on the Catalogue of Soundscape Interventions website features a total of 43 soundscape intervention cases. These cases are distributed across 16 cities spanning 4 continents, showcasing a diverse and global representation of soundscape projects. This extensive collection highlights various approaches to enhancing urban and rural soundscapes, addressing environmental noise, and improving public spaces through auditory experiences.

The detailed information provided for each case includes the project's background, aims, methodologies, and impact on the local community. This data serves as a valuable resource for researchers, urban planners, acoustic engineers, and community activists interested in understanding and implementing soundscape interventions. The database not only acts as a catalogue of past and present projects but also as an inspiration for future soundscape improvements globally.

The screenshot displays the 'Soundscape Interventions Map' interface. At the top, there are buttons for 'Map' and 'List', and a search bar labeled 'Search interventions...'. The map shows a world map with several blue location pins indicating intervention sites in North America, Europe, and Australia. Below the map is an 'Example List' with three entries, each with a 'View' button:

- ▶ **Nauener Platz, Berlin** View
- ▶ **Pavilion of Echoes, Zagreb** View
- ▶ **Sustainable Urban Village, Gainesville** View

Screenshot of the website (<https://soundscapeintervention.org/catalogue/>), showing an excerpt of catalogued soundscape interventions (map + list)

Open for submissions

The Catalogue of Soundscape Interventions website remains open for ongoing submissions of soundscape cases, offering a unique opportunity for individuals and organizations worldwide to contribute to this growing field. Whether you're an urban planner, acoustic designer, researcher, or community activist, your participation is invaluable. By submitting your soundscape intervention project, you contribute to a global knowledge base, helping to share innovative ideas and practices that can benefit communities everywhere.

Invitation

Have you participated in, or do you have info about, a soundscape intervention?
We invite you to contribute to *Catalogue of Soundscape Interventions(CSI)*!

Click the link or scan the QR code below to submit a soundscape intervention project now:

👉 <https://soundscape-intervention.org/submissions/> 👈

You can also share this invitation with anyone who could be interested.
Sincerely appreciate your contribution to the CSI.

Our catalogue includes a wide range of interventions worldwide, from site-specific micro-actions such as parks to large-scale interventions including urban planning projects.

1. <https://soundscape-intervention.org/ex-nauener-platz/>

2. <https://soundscape-intervention.org/ex-sea-organ/>

3. <https://soundscape-intervention.org/>

4. <https://soundscape-intervention.org/ex-sheaf-square/>

5,6. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10062102>

7. Easteal, Matthew, et al. "Urban sound planning in Brighton and Hove." Proceedings of the Forum Acusticum, Krakow, Poland. 2014.

Part 3

Eight dimensions of soundscape interventions

Stages

A crucial factor that distinguishes the practice of soundscape intervention lies in the specific STAGE at which it is considered within the site design. This is because soundscape interventions conceptualized at different stages often have their own unique manifestations. Thus, we categorize the collected soundscape practices based on whether they are considered during the 'planning' stage or the 'implementation' stage.

Planning Stage:

- Integrated into the overall site design.
- Broader, conceptual level.
- Examples: Designating quiet zones, traffic noise buffers.

Implementation Stage:

- Linked with actual construction or post-construction.
- Focus on specific facilities and real conditions.
- Aimed at resolving site-specific issues or enhancing environmental quality through sound design.

Main zones of Urban Village in Gainesville

Ring-shaped audio island Nauener Platz

Contributors

Understanding the **CONTRIBUTORS** involved in a soundscape design project is important because it not only facilitates the project to be found by the appropriate audience, but it also demonstrates that soundscape interventions can benefit from multidisciplinary perspectives, and that innovative approaches can be formed through the collaboration of different professionals.

- **Urban Planners and Architects:** Design and structure the physical environment.
- **Acoustic Engineers:** Manage and improve sound quality.
- **Musicians and Artists:** Bring creative and aesthetic elements.
- **Academics:** Provide research and theoretical insights.
- **Policy Makers:** Influence regulations and support implementation.

Scale

SCALE refers to the spatial extent of soundscape interventions. It is categorized into three levels:

- **Microscale (e.g., pocket garden)**
- **Mesoscale (e.g., city block)**
- **Macroscale (e.g., city)**

Understanding the Scale dimension is crucial as it allows to analyze the impact of soundscape interventions at different spatial levels.

Period of time

The **PERIOD OF TIME** dimension distinguishes between short-term and permanent soundscape interventions. Short-term interventions may be temporary installations or events, while permanent interventions involve long-lasting modifications to the built environment.

Intervention types

Analysing the dimension of the **INTERVENTION TYPE** helps in classifying and understanding the diverse strategies employed in soundscape design.

- **Source Interventions:** Modifying/managing noise sources (e.g., controlling noise emissions).
- **Path/Infrastructure Interventions:** Altering physical infrastructure/layout (e.g., modifying traffic patterns).
- **Integral/Design Interventions:** Holistic approach beyond noise reduction (e.g., improving acoustic and visual environment quality).
- **Receiver Interventions:** Enhancing perception, understanding, and experience of individuals within the soundscape.

Public involvement

By involving the public in soundscape design, decision-making processes become more democratic, and designs become more responsive to the needs and preferences of the community. This dimension emphasizes the importance of engaging stakeholders and the public to identify the most appropriate soundscape interventions.'

- **Formal Application:** Gathering initial public feedback and expectations.
- **Design and Management:** Integrating public input into planning and design.
- **Implementation:** Executing the design with opportunities for public feedback.
- **Assessment:** Evaluating the soundscape's impact using community input.
- **Dissemination:** Sharing outcomes and learnings with the wider community.

Aims & purposes

The **AIMS AND PURPOSE** dimension includes Preservation, Enhancement, Mitigation, Design integration, and Education.

- **Preservation:** Protecting and conserving valuable acoustic environments.
- **Enhancement:** Introducing sound sources; improving soundscape quality and attributes.

- **Mitigation:** Reducing or eliminating unwanted noise.
- **Design Integration:** Creating new, pleasant sound atmospheres.
- **Education:** Raising awareness about the importance of soundscape.

Approaches

APPROACHES refer to the different methodologies and techniques employed in soundscape design. The four identified approaches are Architectural, Mechanical, Electroacoustic, and Biological/Natural.

- **Architectural Approaches:** Designing physical structures and spaces for specific acoustic qualities.
- **Mechanical Approaches:** Utilizing physical and natural forces to create or modify sound experiences.
- **Electroacoustic Approaches:** Using technology and audio systems to shape and enhance soundscapes.
- **Biological/Natural Approaches:** Integrating natural elements and ecosystems for healthy, harmonious sound environments.

Overview of the existing soundscape interventions

Eight dimensions of the 43 soundscape intervention practices in CSI database

Project name	Stages	Contributors	Scale	Period of time	Intervention Type	Public involvement	Aims and purpose	Approach
Arizona Science Center	B	B, C	B	B	D	–	E	B
Bamboo Garden	B	A, B, C	A	B	B/C, D	–	B, D	A, C
Biophony: SoundGarden	B	B, C	A	A	D, E	–	B, E	C, D
Birrarung Marr Park	B	B, C	A	B	D, E	E	B, E	B, C
Blue Moon	B	B, C	B	B	D, E	–	B, C, E	C, B
Ellen Reid Soundwalk	B	B	C	B	E	–	B	C
Fontaine de Milan	B	B	A	B	A, B/C	–	B, C	B
Garden of Sound	B	A	B	B	D	–	B, D	A, D
Harmonic Bridge	B	B, C	B	A	D, E	–	B, E	B, C
Harmonic Conduit	B	B, C	B	A	D, E	–	B	B, C
Heaven's Cloth	B	C	A	A	D	–	B	C
Het Klankenbos Sound Forest	B	B, C	B	B	D, E	–	B	C, B, D
Imagination Playground	A	A, B	B	B	D	–	C, D	A
Jim Ellis Freeway Park	B	A, B	B	B	B/C, D	–	B, C	A
Lincoln Park	B	A, B	B	B	D, E	–	B	A, C
Musical Roads	B	B, C	B	B	A, E	–	B	B
Nauener Platz	B	A, B, D	B	B	B/C, D, E	B, C, D	B, C, D, E	A, C
Neville Stress Underpass	B	A, B, C	B	B	B/C, D, E	–	B, C	C
Pavilion of Echoes	B	A, B	A	B	D	–	A, B, E	A
Pedalling SeaSides	B	B, C	B	A	E	–	B,	C
PS 244 Primary School	B	B	A	B	D, E	–	E	A, B
Salesforce Transit Center	B	B, C	B	B	A, B/C, D	–	B, C	A, B
Sea Cat Tail - Umi Tsukushi	B	A, B	A	B	D, E	–	B, E	B
Schüssinselpark	B	A, E	B	B	D	–	A, D	D
Sea Organ	B	A, B	B	B	D, E	–	B, E	A, B
Sempione Park	B	B, D	B	A	A, D	–	B, E	C

Sheaf Square	B	A, B, D	B	B	B/C, D	–	B, C	A, B
Spritzbrunnen at the Dreirosenanlage	B	A, B	B	B	B/C, D	–	B, C	B
Suspended Sound Line	B	C	A	B	D, E	–	D	A
Sustainable Urban Village	A	A, D, E	C	B	A, B/C, D	B, C	A, B, C, D	A, D
Sydney Modern Project	B	B, C	A	B	B/C, D, E	–	D	A
The Music Box Village	B	A, B, C	B	B	D, E	B, C, E	B, D	A, B
The National September 11 Memorial	B	A	B	B	B/C, D	–	B, C	A
Thames Barrier Park	B	A	B	B	B/C, D	B, C, D	B, C, D	A
Time Piece	B	B, C	A	B	D, E	–	B, E	C
Urban Light Contacts	B	B, C	A	A	E	–	B, E	B, C
Urban Sound Planing - Brighton & Hove	A	A, B, D, E	C	B	A, B/C, D, E	B, C, D	A, B, C, D, E	A, C
Vertical Water	B	B, C	A	A	A, D	–	C	A, C
War Damaged Instrument	B	B, C	A	A	E	–	A, B, E	C
Warwick Bar Master Plan	A	A, B, C, D, E	B	B	D, E	–	A, B, C, D	C, D
Water Veil	B	B, C	A	A	B/C, D	–	B, C	B
Whispering Wind	B	B, D	A	B	D, E	–	B, D, E	A
The Musikiosk	B	B, D	B	A	A, E	B, D, E	B, C	C

The classification of the eight dimensions (including number of occurrences):

1. Stages – A: Planning (4), B: Implementation (39).
2. Contributors – A: Urban planners and architects (15), B: Acoustic engineers (36), C: Musicians and artists (23), D: Academics (9), E: Policymakers (4).
3. Scale – A: Microscale (e.g., pocket garden) (16), B: Mesoscale (e.g., city block) (24), C: Macroscale (e.g., city) (3).
4. Period of time – A: Short-term (9), B: Permanent (34).
5. Intervention types – A: Source (7), B/C: Path/Infrastructure (14), D: integral/design (36), E: Receiver (25).
6. Public involvement – A: Formal application (0), B: Design and management (6), C: Implementation (5), D: Assessment (3), E: Dissemination (3).
7. Aims and purpose – A: Preservation (6), B: Enhancement (36), C: Mitigation (17), D: Design integration (14), E: Education (17).
8. Approaches – A: Architectural (21), B: Mechanical (18), C: Electroacoustic (21), D: Biological/natural (7).

(<https://soundscape-intervention.org/>, retrieved August 2023)

Overview of the existing soundscape interventions

The CSI database categorizes soundscape interventions across eight dimensions, mainly in the implementation stage of site design, indicating a focus on practical application. Contributors are mostly acoustic engineers, musicians/artists, urban planners/architects, and academics, with limited policymaker involvement. Soundscape practices are inclusive and multidisciplinary, emphasizing neighborhood-level interventions (mesoscale) for immediate local impact. Most interventions are permanent, showing a long-term commitment to soundscape improvement. The most common intervention types are integral/design, targeting the overall soundscape and the receivers' experience.

- **Majority Stage:** Implementation (39/43 cases)
- **Primary Contributors:** Acoustic engineers (36), Musicians/Artists (23), Urban planners/Architects (15), Academics (9)
- **Policy Makers' Involvement:** Low, mainly in planning, larger projects
- **Nature of Contributions:** Diverse and multidisciplinary, enhancing holistic understanding
- **Scale of Interventions:** Mostly mesoscale (e.g., city block, 24 cases), followed by microscale (e.g., pocket garden, 16 cases), and macroscale (e.g., city, 3 cases)
- **Duration of Interventions:** Mostly permanent (34 cases), indicating long-term commitment over short-term solutions (9 cases)
- **Types of Interventions:** Mostly integral/design (36 cases), then receiver (25 cases), path/infrastructure (14 cases), and source (7 cases)
- **Main approaches:** Shaping overall soundscape through design and targeting receivers' experience.

The taxonomy wheel derived from the 43 CSI cases, depicting the eight dimensions (inner ring) and the distribution of their respective manifestations A-E (outer ring)

Common strategies

Based on the analysis and categorization of 43 soundscape intervention instances in our database, we distilled common strategies inherent to four types of soundscape interventions

<p style="text-align: center;">SOURCE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Sound identification and preservation• Noise reduction and masking• Sound installations powered by nature (e.g., light, wind, tides, vibrations)• Sound facilities (e.g., loudspeakers, audio island)• Introducing additional sound sources (e.g., natural sounds, meaningful sound to the site)	<p style="text-align: center;">PATH/INFRASTRUCTURE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Noise control plan (e.g., buffer zone design, blocking facilities)• Hard noise barriers (e.g., topography, sound barrier)• Soft noise barriers (e.g., greenery)• Noise absorption material
<p style="text-align: center;">INTEGRAL/DESIGN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Sound environment assessment• Space planning (e.g., planning for quiet areas.)• Acoustic design of the space (e.g., quiet area, water sounds, amplified echo)• Electroacoustic system (e.g., outdoor theatre)• Biodiversity design	<p style="text-align: center;">RECEIVER</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Activity preservation and encouragement• Interactive sound installations• Immersive sound experience (e.g., loudspeaker system)

Common strategies used in soundscape interventions based on 43 real-world examples, retrieved August 2023

Sound Source Interventions:

- **Amplifying Desired Sounds:** Enhance existing natural site sounds.
- **Adding Preferable Sounds:** Use sound-emitting devices (natural or electroacoustic) to introduce new sounds.
- **Mitigating Unwanted Sounds:** Plan to remove or mask noise sources.

Sound Propagation Interventions:

- **Noise Buffer Zones:** Manage noise over larger areas.
- **Noise Barriers:** Utilize hard (terrain modifications, sound barriers) and soft (greenery) barriers.
- **Sound-Absorbing Materials:** Reduce noise impact.

Comprehensive Site Design:

- **Combined Strategies:** Merge source, path, and receiver approaches.
- **Spatial Sound Plans:** Design quiet areas, use water sounds, amplify unique site sounds.
- **Electroacoustic Systems:** Enhance acoustic quality without altering space.
- **Biodiversity Design:** Attract diverse wildlife to create a harmonious soundscape.

Recipient-Centered Interventions:

- **Preserve Human Activities:** Recognize human interactions as key sound components.
- **Interactive Sound Devices:** Focus on human interaction with site sounds.
- **Immersive Experiences:** Enhance individual sound experiences.

The current state of soundscape interventions and lessons learned

- **Soundscape Interventions in Early Planning**

Presently, few soundscape interventions are considered at the initial planning stage of a site. This trend is attributed to the novelty of the field. However, with increasing evidence of their efficacy, their incorporation in early planning stages is expected to grow.

- **Practitioner Dominance**

The field is currently dominated by environmental designers and sound professionals, such as architects and sound engineers. Policymakers are less involved, leading to a focus on smaller spatial scales in designs.

- **Need for Collaboration**

Effective soundscape intervention requires a collaboration between policymakers and practitioners. Practical experience informs policy formulation, while policies guide project execution.

- **Diversity in Intervention Types**

Soundscape interventions are diverse and complex, making categorization challenging. Most interventions involve comprehensive environmental transformation or focus on enhancing interaction with the environment. Few target noise source reduction directly.

- **Electroacoustic Methods and Sustainability**

Electroacoustic methods are popular due to their immediate and controllable impact, but they entail higher maintenance costs and energy consumption. Conversely, biological/natural methods, though underused, offer greater sustainability and health benefits, suggesting a need for their increased utilization in future projects.

Part 4

Suggestions for practitioners

Utilization of the website and database

Regular Access and Updates

- **Frequent visit**

This database remains open for the submission of soundscape practice cases. Periodically, cases that meet the criteria will be recorded in the database and posted on the website. Therefore, it would be advantageous for practitioners to frequently visit the website to keep abreast of the latest advancements in soundscape interventions. This ensures they stay informed about the most recent methods, research results, and case studies from around the world.

- **Contribution to database**

Practitioners are strongly urged to contribute their own soundscape intervention projects, as well as projects they were involved in or have observed, to the database. By doing so, they not only enhance the richness of the database but also facilitate the sharing of a wide array of experiences and insights within the community. This collaboration not only fosters a more comprehensive understanding of soundscape practices but also encourages a vibrant exchange of ideas, techniques, and perspectives.

Efficient Search and Categorization

- **Advanced Search Features:**

In Part 3 of this report, we have compiled and summarized all the existing cases from the database into a table. This classification is designed for better understanding. Such categorization aids practitioners in swiftly locating pertinent examples and insights that correspond to their ongoing projects or research interests. During the case retrieval process, practitioners can find relevant cases based on eight different dimensions. To locate the needed cases, they can enter the names of these cases in the 'Catalogue—Search Interventions' section on the website.

Moreover, the website features the geographical locations of all cases, allowing users to conveniently locate soundscape intervention practices in specific regions when needed.

Learning and Inspiration

- **Case Studies as Learning Tools:**

In soundscape intervention design, practitioners should look beyond replicating similar cases and instead draw from a broad spectrum of existing practices. By studying diverse interventions and their unique approaches and outcomes, they can gain valuable insights for their own projects. This database helps in understanding various strategies used in different contexts and the impact these have on communities and environments

Furthermore, the practices in this database involve a range of contributors. Practitioners are urged to seek **interdisciplinary insights** from areas like urban planning, environmental psychology, acoustic engineering, and community arts. Engaging in such cross-disciplinary exploration promotes innovative thinking and expands the scope of application in their soundscape projects.

Networking and Collaboration

- **Direct author contact**

We advise utilizing the clear source citations in the database not only for their reliability and credibility but also to facilitate smooth interaction with original project contributors. Engaging in such collaboration and knowledge exchange is crucial for gaining an in-depth understanding of each project's context, challenges, and strategies.

- **Feedback**

Practitioners are encouraged to promptly contact us with any feedback regarding their use of the CSI database. By doing so, users of the CSI database can also contribute to its development. This collaborative approach not only improves the tool but also fosters a sense of community among its users. Practitioners' active participation in providing feedback and suggestions ensures the database continuously evolves, making it a more effective and responsive resource for everyone involved

Application of soundscape intervention strategies

Maximizing Insights from Case Studies:

- **Dive deep into related Case**

In Part 3 of this report (P.20), we summarize several frequently used strategies, focusing on four key aspects: source, path/infrastructure, integral/design, and receiver. This serves as a foundational knowledge base for practitioners in their design process. It's important to note that we cannot distinguish which strategy is superior, as the choice and application of these strategies are often closely linked to the context. Therefore, practitioners, when considering which strategy to use, should first deeply investigate related cases. They should aim to understand not only what was done but also why and how it was effective. This approach provides a solid knowledge foundation for building their own interventions.

- **Learn from Comparisons**

On the other hand, learning from comparisons is crucial. Practitioners should comparatively analyze cases to identify successful strategies and unique methods that align with their project's specific needs. Understanding how these strategies are applied in various settings can inspire innovative ideas tailored to their own context.

Tailoring Strategies to Fit Your Environment:

- **Adapt with Sensitivity**

As you borrow strategies from the database, remember to adapt them to your local context. Consider cultural, environmental, and social nuances to ensure your intervention is well-received and effective.

- **Test Before Full Implementation:**

If feasible, start with small-scale pilot testing to assess and refine the effectiveness of your strategies. This step is crucial for fine-tuning your approach before scaling up.

Innovation and Exploration

As practitioners in the evolving field of soundscape interventions, you are positioned at the forefront of an exciting and dynamic area of study. This unique position offers you the opportunity to not only apply established practices but also to pioneer new methodologies and approaches. Encourage yourself and your team to think outside the box. Look beyond traditional methods and consider how new technologies, interdisciplinary approaches, or untested strategies could bring about more impactful soundscape changes.

Community engagement and documentation

The existing database in the CSI project, while comprehensive in various aspects of soundscape interventions, reveals a notable shortfall in the area of community engagement. Current practices documented in the database often overlook the vital role of community input and participation, both in the design and post-implementation phases of soundscape interventions. This lack of focus on user feedback and continuous community involvement limits our understanding of how these interventions are received and their long-term effectiveness in different community settings.

- **Recognizing the Importance of Community Feedback**

As practitioners, it is essential to understand that soundscape interventions are not just about altering physical spaces but also about influencing the community's auditory experience. Thus, post-implementation feedback from those living or working in these spaces is invaluable for assessing the true effectiveness of your intervention.

- **Enhanced Focus on Post-Implementation Surveys**

Post-implementation, it's essential to conduct follow-up studies to assess how the intervention has been integrated into the daily lives of community members. This not only helps in evaluating the success of the project but also in identifying areas for improvement.

- **Documenting and Sharing**

Contribute back to the CSI database by thoroughly documenting your methods and findings related to community engagement. This will help fill the current gap in the database and provide valuable insights for other practitioners.

Part 5

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**Catalogue of
Soundscape Interventions**

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